

Report - Experiment Design Data Science*

*Deep Learning over Multi-field Categorical Data

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Abstract—In this report we describe our reproducing approach of the experiment in the given paper addressing conversion rates on published advertisements [1]. The given data set was used to train different models in order to compare the results to linear models currently used in the industry for this topic. The main purpose was to prove that deep neural networks can predict user behaviour more accurately, measured in AUC scores, than linear models. In this report we outline how we were able to achieve similar results by using a smaller portion of the data set.

Index Terms—data science, experiment, reproduction, dataset, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

In many web-applications predicting user behaviour, especially clicking-rates on online advertisements is a crucial part for the regarding companies. Existing prediction models often take a linear approach, which is powerful in calculation but the results lack in accuracy [1]. That is why the experiment tackles this issue by using deep neural networks, that are able to learn from user's advertisement clicks and the corresponding categorical features. This paper compares the performance of a factorisation-machine supported Neural Network, a sample-based Neural Network and the more conservative approaches of a Logistic Regression and a Factorisation Machine Model.

The capability of identifying relevant ads and predicting user's interactions are the main concerns for this experiment. Each click delivers categorical features, such as user IP, ad size, ad format, user tags etc [1]. In the experimental setup section it is described in detail how the value pairs were used in the paper.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The paper provides a link to a GitHub repository [2], which includes a portion of the iPinYou dataset and some Python scripts to demonstrate the procedures described in the work. In particular, the data provided is a portion of the full dataset, focusing only on the advertiser with the ID 2997. The Python scripts that are used to train and evaluate the various models,

were also targeted at this specific demo dataset.

In total, five models are evaluated and compared on five different advertisers (in the paper). First, a simple and fast logistic regression model (LR). Then, also a factorisation machine (FM), which is non-linear and used to estimate the features. Based on this FM, there is the Factorisation-machine supported neural network (FNN), which is a hybrid model. It is described in the paper [1] itself, which can be read by the interested reader. Last but not least, two sampling-based neural network models (SNN) are evaluated. One of them is labelled RBM and one DAE. The exact definitions can also be looked up in the original work [1]. In order to compare the performance of each model for each advertiser the paper uses the area under ROC curve (AUC) metric.

Our goal was to reproduce the evaluation results of the paper, with a high accuracy but also with a limited amount of time and with limited resources. There were some major challenges along the way. First of all, as already mentioned, the linked GitHub repository [2] has a very small portion of the dataset and only contains demo code, not the actual code that was used for the original experiment. Furthermore, the codebase was outdated (Python 2.7) and had a couple of misleading and buggy lines in it. It ran out-of-the-box with the demo data, but it was more difficult to get the code to work with additional data. An additional challenge on the side was, that one of our colleagues left in the middle of the process, which left us with even fewer resources.

III. OBTAINING & TRANSFORMING DATA

Obtaining the full dataset in the first place was not an easy task. The link provided in the GitHub repository led to a Chinese website that was not very trustworthy and impossible to navigate for our team. Other links in the repository were completely unavailable. We finally found the full dataset on Kaggle [3] and it consisted of 19.5 million instances and had a significant size.

However, the problem here was that the iPinYou dataset naturally has a very different structure than the one used in the demo repository. In order to get the dataset to structured

more like the demo data, we needed to clone another GitHub repository, provided in the first one, called `make-ipinyou-data` [4]. The code there took the full dataset, unzipped the individual files and structured them into individual folders based on the advertiser IDs. After this step, we had a structure, which was approximating the one of the demo repository. Since the paper only compares five advertisers, we deleted the irrelevant directories and focused on the ones that were important for reproducing the results.

We replaced the original data folder with the folder of the respective advertiser, for each iteration. Since the code base was basically undocumented, we had a hard time figuring out, which script needs to run first and what parameters are important. For example, the script, for the factorisation machine not only trained and evaluated the model itself but also provided the base model for the FNN. However, it only outputs the model file, if exactly ten parameters are passed. Because of such details, we spent a lot of time trying to decipher what the code was meant to do.

A. Sampling Data

The dataset we worked with was huge and our team of two was limited to our own private devices. Running all the models on all the data would have used up a lot of time and resources. So, we decided to randomly sample instances from the training and testing data for each advertiser and work with 20-30 percent of the data. This of course leads to deviations in the results but it is still representative. To do the sampling we wrote a Python script, which randomly selects the necessary amount of lines from the data files.

The sampling scripts however, were not only relevant to get a smaller portion of the data but also to reformat the individual lines. In order to bring the generated training and testing data files into the right format, we needed to remove the second column.

IV. FACTORISATION MACHINE

After we finally understood what the code was doing and how the data ought to be structured training and evaluating the FM model was quite easy, since we were able to just run the script. However, to export the final model into a text file, we needed to provide many of the previously generated files and also additional parameters, like a results file, dl files, log files and the feature index.

Once all this was done, we were able to evaluate the model and write down our results. As already mentioned, the data was randomly sampled and only a portion of the data was used. Thus, the results are to be taken with a grain of salt and with a different random sample, the scores might be different. We decided, to write down our first try.

V. LOGISTIC REGRESSION MODEL

In order to build up the regression model we first tried to implement the logistic regression with a python library

called **sklearn**. The main problem with this approach was, in spite of the straight forward implementation, the data transformation. The models implemented in the paper did not take big advantage of existing Python libraries in order to implement their prediction models, so the work process was a different one than building a **panda** data frame and feed the data into a model like **sklearn's** linear logistic regression.

The results of the first approach was not accurate and did not match the scores mentioned in the paper. Hence we tried a different approach and took a closer look at the existing **FM.py** file, that was used by the publishers to build the factorisation machine model. We took the data preparation methods and shifted them into a new Python script. After studying the factorisation machine implementation, we then found some helpful functions in the script that were not used for the FM approach, but seem to work for a linear approach. The logistic regression was partly implemented in the script file but never used, so we cleaned up the script, shifted the help full methods into the new logistic regression file and were able to build up the model without any third party libraries and run it on the data set. The results were a lot better than the ones achieved in the first approach, so we decided to stick to this implementation.

VI. FACTORISATION MACHINE SUPPORTED NEURAL NETWORK

As mentioned before and as the name already suggests, the FNN model is based on the FM model. Understanding how this is handled in the demo repository was a challenge, due to the lack of documentation. The FM model script outputs a model text file (if ten parameters are passed), which is then used as the basis for the FNN script. The problem here however was that the model file that was generated based on our downloaded dataset, was in some aspects different to the one in the demo set. The main reason for that was the different feature index file and the missing formatted feature index file. Because of that some minor changes (like removing the first line) had to be made to the model file.

Having done that, the challenge was not to get the FNN script to run with the constructed data and model. For this, we had to remove or comment out individual lines that were specifically targeted at the demo data. One line for example was checking if the advertiser ID is 2997 and only if that is the case, it sets the parameters for the model. Furthermore, we needed to remove the dictionary that was used to translate labels to numbers, since our model was missing the labels that were only provided for the dataset.

VII. EVALUATION

Unfortunately, due to time constraints and one team member spontaneously leaving our team during the process, we were not able to get the SNN scripts to work with the additional data. Thus, we were only able to evaluate or

reproduce the results for the LR, FM and FNN models.

First, we tried an ineffective approach for the logistic regression model as described in the respective section. For this approach the numbers were very bad and we were not able to reproduce the results.

Advertiser	LR	
	Paper	Our Results (OR)
1458	70.42	46.03
2259	69.66	44.87
2261	62.03	48.21
2997	60.77	45.02
3386	80.30	49.43

After changing the approach and rewriting the code that was provided in the FM script, the results became much better. For the FM and FNN script, the rewriting of the code and the reformatting of the output files was sufficient to achieve the desirable performance as well. The comparison with the original results [1] can be seen below.

Advertiser	LR		FM		FNN	
	Paper	OR	Paper	OR	Paper	OR
1458	70.42	67.88	70.21	70.78	70.52	70.21
2259	69.66	67.67	69.73	70.02	69.74	69.98
2261	62.03	62.45	60.97	60.02	62.99	62.13
2997	60.77	60.43	60.87	60.54	61.41	60.27
3386	80.30	74.79	79.05	74.94	80.56	80.08

All in all, we were able to somewhat reproduce the results with only 20-30 percent of the dataset. Deviations in both directions may have happened due to the incomplete and randomly sampled data. But the results should still be representative and are quite close to the ones in the paper.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Reproducing the results of a paper, which was released about five years ago was way more difficult than expected. Some of the provided links were inactive, outdated or unusable for us. The code base was outdated (Python 2.7) and almost undocumented. The dataset [3] was also mostly undocumented. The experiment and the steps were outlined in the paper [1] but the provided code was only a very narrow demo example, which was not easily scaleable. All of these things combined with a team member leaving during the process made reproducing the results harder than expected.

We also saw that it is possible to somewhat reproduce the results with only 20-30 percent of the data and we used this approach to save a lot of time and resources.

REFERENCES

- [1] Deep Learning over Multi-field Categorical Data. Weinan Zhang, Tianming Du, Jun Wang. ECIR, 2016.
- [2] GitHub Repository: <https://github.com/wnzhang/deep-ctr>
- [3] iPinYou Dataset: <https://www.kaggle.com/lastsummer/ipinyou>
- [4] Make iPinYou: <https://github.com/wnzhang/make-ipinyou-data>